

Proposal: Racial, Equity, and Inclusion Center Pilot

Recently, Oregon Health & Science University (OHSU) decided to focus on becoming an anti-racist institution. In order to do this, it is critical to use a racial equity lens to craft and guide this work. This, in part means addressing the many ways that systemic racism¹ manifests: Individual, interpersonal, institutional, and structural. The student-led volunteer group Alliance for Visible Diversity in Science (AVDS; established in 2016) developed a proposal² that outlines a model for structural changes, via implementation of multiple racial equity and inclusion (REI centers) that would allow OHSU to address racial equity for all OHSU members (e.g., learners, faculty, and staff).

The REI centers are modeled after and informed by the years of on-campus racial equity work that AVDS has done over the last four years. Each center consists of three critical aspects of racial equity work: data collection and analysis, community transformation, and innovative policy. Notably, because the proposal represents a different approach to racial equity, some may consider its implementation as a risky endeavor. However, the authors see the potential for high reward because the model addresses several limitations in the way OHSU currently addresses racial equity including: building community and trust within the local community; creating a sense of shared responsibility; making data-driven decisions; and specifically focusing on policy reform, to name a few.

In an effort to take immediate actionable steps towards racial equity and inclusion, the creation of an REI center pilot offers an attractive next step. A pilot will provide an example of how to implement an REI center, create a mechanism to collect preliminary and continuous data, provide a comparison for other racial equity strategies on campus, and create content that could be shared and adopted in other campus initiatives. The Vollum Institute presents the optimal setting for the pilot as there is both momentum from the bottom up and commitment from the top down in progressing towards realizing anti-racism within the organization. The primary aims of the pilot involve: (i) collecting and analyzing relevant data in order to make data-driven decisions regarding cultural transformation and policy change; (ii) shifting the institutional culture towards racial inclusion via community engagement and education; and (iii) reviewing and establishing innovative policy for faculty, staff, and graduate students. By the end of a 3-5-year period, we will have created a sustainable environment that centers racial equity and inclusion within the Vollum Institute.

Overall Aims:

1. **Community Transformation:** Addressing internalized and interpersonal racism requires education and community trust. Working beside local communities provides a pathway to educational/training and establishes community participation which allows for a collaborative and inclusive community building - a critical aspect for community transformation. Data collected will provide insights into innovative initiatives to pursue. *Outcome:* This aim will build community and create a shared sense of responsibility. Major goals will be to (i) develop formal and standardized data collection procedures for assessing the organizational culture, (ii) increase community racial equity education and empower community members to become active agents of

1. Pittsburgh Arts Council. Levels of Racism.

http://www.pittsburghartscouncil.org/storage/documents/Capacity_Building/LevelsofRacism.pdf

2. Alliance for Visible Diversity in Science. (2020, July 9). Revisioning OHSU's approach to racial diversity, equity, and inclusion. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3937800>

change and (iii) obtain increasingly positive feedback from racial and ethnic minorities within the Vollum Institute.

2. **Innovative Policy:** Depending on their design, our policies either directly uphold or actively dismantle systemic and institutionalized racism. Community engagement and input (data) captured through the efforts of the transformation aim and by review of internal operations will highlight current policies incongruent with racial equity. In addition, this data provides a focal point for the creation and establishment of equitable and well-researched policies that reflect values of Vollum Institute members towards an anti-racist organization. *Outcome:* Major goals will be to (i) develop formal and standardized data collection procedures and (ii) measure increased recruitment and retention of learners, faculty, and staff from racial/ethnic minority backgrounds.

Director of Community Transformation

General Description

The Racial Equity and Inclusion (REI) Center pilot, housed in the Vollum Institute, is responsible for building a high-performance culture that reflects the Vollum Institute's values and commitment to racial equity and anti-racism. The Vollum Institute is a uniquely beneficial setting for the establishment of an REI center pilot because it consists of staff and faculty which will allow for a focus on racial equity as it pertains to researchers with different roles. The Vollum Institute is also an attractive pilot site because it houses the Neuroscience Graduate Program which will allow for development of racial equity advancement specific for learners. As the pilot is implemented, procedural documentation and the creation of new methods/tools for racial equity in the academic research setting can be simultaneously tested and shared with the broader OHSU community. The Director of Community Transformation has the responsibility to evaluate the current institutional culture, develop and implement strategies to increase racial equity education, and create strategies and pathways to increase the overall community participation in racial equity work.

The Director of Community Transformation is an essential member of the REI Center pilot, who works closely with the REI Center Director of Innovative Policy, Director(s) of the Vollum Institute, and who is a supervisor to the REI Center research assistant.

The Director of Community Transformation is primarily involved with using a racial equity lens to assess the current institutional culture, determine cultural values and processes incongruent with racial equity, and develop strategic pathways to align cultural norms and practices with a racially inclusive environment for students, staff, and faculty.

The Director of Community Transformation is appointed by, and reports to, the Director(s) of the Vollum Institute and the Chief Research Officer.

FTE/Funding: 1.0 FTE

Primary responsibilities:

- Initiate or strengthen community relationships within the Vollum Institute and develop strategies to empower community members to participate in racial equity work (30% FTE)
- Establish a clear vision and priorities (i.e., values and mission) for the continuous improvement of racial equity within the Vollum Institute (20% FTE)
- Engage Vollum Institute community in education on racial equity (20% FTE)
- Reinforce a culture of feedback by creating a structure of transparency and learning mindsets (20% FTE)
- Cultivate a strong and transparent working relationship with the Vollum Institute director(s) and ensure open communication about the measurement of financial, programmatic, and impact performance against stated milestones and goals (10% FTE)

Qualifications:

- Graduate degree (PhD in Biomedical Science preferred)
- Minimum 5 years of experience working with people of multiple cultures and backgrounds; identifying intersectionality to help support organizational members
- Minimum 5 years of experience in community leadership and organization; including experience in initiating, building, and delivering social change management and racial inclusion programming
- Experience in policy advocacy and campaigns

We anticipate candidates will have:

- Strong written, oral, and team communication skills, ability to build consensus
- Base knowledge of cultural competencies, systemic racism, and intersecting systems of oppression (i.e., colonialism, patriarchal, classism, white supremacy, heterosexism, ableism, etc.)
- Strong understanding of research culture and academic systems
- Ability to exhibit a strong equity lens in every interaction with students, staff, and faculty
- Strong emotional intelligence, with the ability to foster an environment and culture that supports people from all communities in developing their voice, generates action-oriented problem-solving, and values transparent communication, flexibility, and authenticity
- Exceptional interpersonal and communication skills, including the ability to work effectively with a broad range of stakeholders by building trust, buy-in, and effective, authentic relationships
- Ability to work collegially and implement change in a multidisciplinary setting

Director of Innovative Policy

General Description

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The Director of Innovative Policy is an essential member of the REI Center pilot, who works closely with the REI Center Director of Community Transformation, Director(s) of the Vollum Institute, and who is a supervisor to the REI Center research assistant.

The Director of Innovative Policy role primarily involves using a racial equity lens to comprehensively review and revise current policies affecting Vollum Institute students, faculty, and staff.

The Director of Innovative Policy is appointed by, and reports to, the Director(s) of the Vollum Institute and the Chief Research Officer.

FTE/Funding: 1.0 FTE

Primary responsibilities:

- Establish a clear vision and priorities (i.e., values and mission) for the continuous improvement of racial equity within the Vollum Institute (30% FTE)
- Advance a strategy and commitment to embed racial equity into the Vollum Institute's internal and external operations in support of progressive workplace policies (20%)
- Identify and build necessary internal systems, staffing structure, operational plans, and best practices to achieve organizational effectiveness and efficiency with regard to racial equity (20%)
- Reinforce a culture of feedback by creating a structure of transparency and learning mindsets (20% FTE)
- Cultivate a strong and transparent working relationship with the Vollum Institute director(s) and ensure open communication about the measurement of financial, programmatic, and impact performance against stated milestones and goals (10% FTE)

Qualifications:

- Graduate degree (PhD in Biomedical Science preferred)
- Minimum 5 years of experience working with people of multiple cultures and backgrounds; identifying intersectionality to help support organizational members
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- Ability to exhibit a strong equity lens in every interaction with students, staff, and faculty
- Strong emotional intelligence, with the ability to foster an environment and culture that supports people from all communities in developing their voice, generates action-oriented problem-solving, and values transparent communication, flexibility, and authenticity
- Exceptional interpersonal and communication skills, including the ability to work effectively with a broad range of stakeholders by building trust, buy-in, and effective, authentic relationships
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Note: Executive Director positions for the [ACLU Portland](#) and [Oregon Consumer Justice](#) were accessed online (downloaded PDF versions available by the authors upon request) and used as a model for describing major responsibilities and required qualifications/preferred expectations relevant to the work of the REI Center Director position descriptions.